

CONTENT, FORMS, METHODS AND TOOLS OF ORGANIZING INTEGRATED LESSONS IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

¹Salaeva Muborak Saburovna, ²Shayunusova Feruza Saxidovna

¹Associate Professor, Department of Psychology, Tashkent University of Applied Sciences

²2nd year student of the Faculty of "Primary Education", Tashkent State Pedagogical University
named after Nizami

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7802799>

Abstract. *The article discusses the implementation of a comprehensive integrative approach in primary education, and also highlights the development of promising integrated educational programs in the native language, reading, literature, education, the outside world, natural science, fine arts in primary education and the provision of scientific knowledge, taking into account the age characteristics of the younger schoolchildren, contributing to the emotional development of the child in the process of teaching these subjects.*

Keywords: *integrated learning; work methodology; holistically integrated approach, reflection of one's own pedagogical activity; psycho-emotional comfort of children in the classroom.*

INTRODUCTION. Education should bring the joy of understanding and communicating with the world in the process of acquiring new knowledge. Every person should have something to be proud of and feel joy in the success of each work. And of course, this feeling of joy makes him more interested in learning and searching.

In recent years, special attention has been paid to the issues of implementing a complex integrative approach to teaching subjects in primary education.

In our opinion, the most effective way is to integrate primary education facilities. Because in order for a student of junior school age to have a holistic perception of the world around him, there should be no boundaries between objects [3].

An integrative approach to education is increasingly recognized as an urgent need of modern education. An analysis of programs in different academic subjects shows that they provide opportunities to use the integration process. When studying each subject, we can see their "interdependence". However, these topics rarely coincide with the time being discussed, and there is also no complete agreement on the content of the issues raised. In order to overcome the barriers between the subjects, they are united around the main concepts and topics. Looking at this topic from different angles allows us to reveal its relationships.

So, subjects should interact in integrated education. At the same time, the topics should be coordinated in terms of content, structure, and the amount of time allocated to study the object or event reflected in it.

Here, we consider integrated education as a system of lessons that combines knowledge in separate subjects and ensures interdependence, on the basis of which children form a holistic perception of the world.

Research in this area shows that an effective way to implement educational functions is to promote educational problems that are common to a number of subjects and to make them

consistent in the interrelationship of the system of lessons in different subjects. In order to eliminate the gap between separate academic subjects, it is necessary to teach in such a way that interrelated subjects complement each other organically, to analyze the studied events and laws based on the achievements of modern science. Such activities should help to form the skills and abilities to consider events in their interrelationship and interdependence, and to develop students' dialectical thinking on the basis of multifaceted knowledge.

Integration at different levels of education has its own characteristics. In the case of integrated education in primary grades, all elements of the educational material should be designed as a whole, interdependent study, from the initial stage to the opening of the whole world for the child. Therefore, it is appropriate to build integrated education in primary education based on the integration of very close fields of knowledge.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS: In recent years, education has become such a scientific direction that it is focused on ensuring the overall intellectual development of a person in the process of learning. Practicing pedagogues identified the contradiction in the conditions of the development of the young generation receiving education. Based on their experience, they believed that it is necessary to carry out the integration of science on the basis of deep methodology.

In the content of the newly developing science, there is a combination of ideas and methods that appeared in different philosophical currents, which requires not only natural adaptation, but also continental adaptation.

Until today, the concept of integration has been widely studied by many researchers-scientists.

The concept of "integration" comes from the Latin "integrafilio" - restoration, filling, "ration" - full meaning.

Therefore, integration means "uniting into a whole, unity of any elements, restoring some kind of unity."

Integration is a higher form of intersubjective communication at a qualitatively new stage of the process of convergence and communication of disciplines that occurs along with the processes of differentiation, and contributes to the creation of a new whole block, an alloy of knowledge, which creates the foundations of worldview and accompanies a person throughout his life.

The concept of "integration" was explained by Spencer as early as the 18th century. A theory of learning in integrative education describes a movement toward holistic lessons that help students. This concept of higher education differs from the "holistic curriculum" movement of primary and secondary schools.

Integrative studies usually involve combining separate topics so that students can gain a more meaningful and authentic understanding.

Russian scientists T.Kun and V.S.Stopin combined philosophy, natural and cultural sciences in the context of integrated education. They thereby made the models of physics into an advanced science to which the modern human mind refers.

In the middle of the 20th century, cybernetics took a high place among advanced sciences. The principles mastered in cybernetics found their application in the explanation of phenomena in the inorganic world in the connections between biological and technical sciences. N. Boming's principle of complementarity in non-classical physics was previously defined by scientists as a

philosophical principle expressing the general laws of nature. This laid the foundation for the development of other sciences in the future. In the process of forming the laws of science, science began to become multifaceted, and the image of man was embodied in it more. As a result, it became necessary to strengthen the process of integration and search for cultural categories that organize human experience.

The foundational structural elements of integration presented by modern philosophy include perfection of worldview. They define meaning, understanding and a person's way of seeing the world. The socialization of a young person can be achieved with the help of the educational system, when the conditions are created to master the perfections of the worldview.

Matrices based on perfections are the basis of various concrete activities, knowledge, ideals, forms. Excellence in the content of education, divided into departments, should cover all its laws. The integrative value of perfection is manifested in all areas of culture. Their mastery manifests itself in the study of any subject.

At present, in pedagogical practice, research on the ways of integration of the educational process on the basis of interdisciplinarity is ongoing. The educational significance of the researches in this regard is great. The problem of the integration of content and educational goals can be solved only on the basis of educational philosophy. Integration describes all areas of human activity today. These areas of activity changed, and actual problems of the time were born. These problems remind us that nature and man exist in a single system and connection, and require scientific knowledge for human existence [2].

METHODS: analysis of historical, retrospective and theoretical-methodological sources, summarization and interpretation of the obtained data, observation, interview, questionnaire, content analysis, qualitative and expert assessment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: Integration in primary education allows to move from local, individual consideration of various phenomena of reality to their interrelated and holistic study. Scientific knowledge, mother tongue, reading, literature, education, the world around us, natural science, visual arts, technology, which contribute to the emotional development of the child, taking into account the age characteristics of students of junior school age, in the organization of integrated education It is possible to show the world in all its diversity by involving the theater in the teaching of music, physical education. This kind of integrated education in primary grades serves to develop the personality of a student of junior school age and to form his creative thinking [4].

Therefore, the introduction of the integration system into education is more likely than the traditional teaching process to form a holistic worldview of students of junior school age, independent systematization of their knowledge, and a scholar who has a non-traditional approach to solving problems. can help to educate the individual. For this, the pedagogue should present the knowledge related to the content of the educational material to the learners not as information they already know and have heard, but in a surprising way [5].

For example: In the scope of the world around us and natural sciences - "Where else is such a place and where can it be? What does it look like and what sounds does it have?" and so on.

Requirements for planning, organizing and conducting integrated lessons:

- defining a system of integrated lessons for the whole year within each class;
- careful planning of each lesson based on an integrative approach, highlighting the main and relevant goals;

- modeling the content of lessons based on an integrative approach, filling them only with content that supports the main goal;
- careful selection of the type and structure of the integrated lesson, teaching methods and tools;
- to make impressions on students of junior school age based on educational assignments suitable for their age and individual-psychological characteristics [6].

The methodology of working in such classes not only gives the pedagogue the opportunity to make extensive use of educational technology, work with problem tasks and books, visualize the educational process, teach in a group, but also includes activities in connection with independent creative work outside the classroom.

In the organization of integrated education, the following principle should be strictly followed, i.e., the main content of the subject should not be squeezed out or confusedly replaced when the content of related subjects included as additions to the teaching process of a particular subject is being studied [7]. In our opinion, this form of integrated education is very suitable for primary classes, it provides an environment that reveals all aspects of children's abilities that cannot be manifested in the form of traditional education. However, at this point, the pedagogue should not forget about another task in his work, that is, moral education of children.

In modern pedagogical literature, the issue of eliminating egocentrism of children, educating them to empathize, and the ability to emotionally relate to other people's experiences (EQ) is being actively discussed. From this point of view, poems and prose texts, reproductions of paintings, fragments of musical works included in the content of integrated education should not be simple illustrations of the studied information [8].

The teacher should be able to show each student that not only he, but also a student of junior school age admires the colors and sounds of nature, that our ancestors experienced reverent pleasure from these situations, and that all his peers in the class can experience the same feelings. The principle of combining several subjects in primary education is aimed at establishing a dialogue on a given topic, in which the topic-specific content, image, emotional state, moral and aesthetic meaning are given. It consists of several basic expressions, which mainly allow objects to enter into dialogue based on basic and figurative-verbal signs.

The teacher must be able to show each student that not only he, but also a student of junior school age admires the colors and sounds of nature, that our ancestors feel reverent pleasure from such situations, and that all peers in the class feel it. The principle of combining several educational subjects in primary education is aimed at establishing a dialogue on a given topic, in which the content, image, emotional state, moral-aesthetic meaning of the topic is given. It consists of several basic phrases, which mainly allow objects to enter into dialogue based on basic and figurative-verbal signs.

Therefore, the importance of integrated classes in primary education is great, and they also have a positive effect on the development of students' independence, knowledge activity and interests. In the content of integrated education in elementary grades, the teacher's pedagogical activity is distinguished by the fact that it is focused on the personality of the student of junior school age [9]. Therefore, this process helps to comprehensively develop the abilities of students of junior school age and activate thinking processes, while encouraging them to generalize their knowledge of various subjects.

Systematic use of integrated lessons makes it possible to widely use various visual aids. Today, as an integrated education in primary classes, pedagogues include "The world around us", "Art work" in the content of the subjects of mother tongue, reading, literature, education, the world around us, natural science, visual arts, technology, music, physical education. , "Introduction to the environment", "Motherland", "Music and movement" integrated topics should be absorbed and effectively used. Also "Word Workshop", "Verb and Love", "Letter", "Artistic Culture", "World and Man", "I and the Surrounding World", "World, Nature and Me", "I and the introduction of general topics such as "my world", "Valeology", "Development of abilities" can also be highly effective.

In the development of prospective integrated educational programs in elementary grades, the content of "Fine Art" and "Technology" subjects such as "Aesthetic thinking and artistic work", "Synthesis of art" as an integral course that implements the content of subjects based on the general laws of aesthetics it is appropriate to enter. Because on the basis of this content, students of junior school age can perceive art as a holistic image of the world in an aesthetic context [10]. The purpose of presenting this educational material is to identify and develop the child's personality, his creative potential on the basis of self-development, and to ensure the student's awareness of his own activities.

It is also desirable that these presented topics be equipped as a teaching-methodical complex "Beauty is always with you" consisting of a textbook, workbook and methodical recommendations for grades 1-4. The composition of the program and the harmonious construction of its parts into vertical-horizontal blocks allow the student of junior school age to reflect nature as a whole and to observe its development, comprehensively covering this problem.

In addition, based on an integrated approach, children learn to perceive works of art as a whole, to see aesthetics in the surrounding world and technical structures, and to determine the general laws of the artistic and creative process.

And for the 3rd grade of primary education, in the development of prospective educational programs for teaching mother tongue, reading, literature, education, the world around us, natural science, visual arts, technology and music. Literary reading. We found it permissible to propose the integration of "Theatre" topics. Because within this topic, literature, fine arts, and music have the same goals as many other subjects, opening the creative potential of every child due to the synthetic nature of theater art. and development, helps to form collective relations and communication skills, arouses interest in the world artistic culture through theater and provides primary information about it, teaches a creative attitude to any work, relevance today [11] These topics are that a student of junior school age will become an interesting person with artistic taste as an intelligent, intelligent theater viewer, have versatile knowledge and his own opinion, later, it is important because it is aimed at developing the ability to conduct independent research.

These integrated education programs aim to:

- to create a sufficiently wide and vivid image of the world in which he lives in students of junior school age, to introduce him to a conversation with man and society, nature and science, culture and art;

- development of creative qualities, independent thinking and planning of one's activities;
- formation of communicative qualities and moral values in students of junior school age;
- can be achieved by solving the tasks of developing personal qualities such as kindness, sensitivity, empathy and self-esteem [12].

In order to achieve the set goals and objectives, it is appropriate to organize training sessions using different forms. For example:

- quiz lesson;
- demonstration lesson;
- travel lesson;
- trip lesson outside the city;
- fairy tale lesson and others.

These training sessions can use the following methods and tools: methods of motivation and maintenance, fiction, visual arts, theater arts, music and cinema.

One of the ideas of the integrated education program is to increase the complexity and interest of the educational material. That is, these ideas range from turning games into literary material through improvisation, to stage performances based on stories invented by children. The classroom is equipped with techniques found in the theater (music, scenery, props, costume shops, etc.), and children are drawn into classrooms with such theatrical conditions, in the process they not only listen, but also themselves. they are engaged in sculpting, painting, cutting, gluing and other works with their own hands [13].

At this point, it should be noted that in the proposed integrated educational program, literary reading lessons in grades 1-4 have three didactic (educational, developmental and educational) goals that are interconnected with theater. providing constructive learning material is the main one.

Aesthetic objects in the works of writers, poets, painters, composers and artists serve to expand the worldview of students of junior school age. Also, through the work of representatives of this talent, students reveal their creative side, and form a positive emotional attitude towards the effort, time and labor spent by them for each work [14].

At the end of the year, on the basis of this integrated educational program, with the participation of all students: organize events by reciting the best numbers, poems, and showing excerpts from plays; it is advisable to organize an exhibition of works on posters, programs, tickets, scenes, costume sketches.

CONCLUSION: It is of particular importance to ensure the integration of the mother tongue, reading, literature, education, the world around us, natural science, visual arts, technology and music in an aesthetic direction in primary grades. Because the above-mentioned integrated educational activities help the students of junior school age to penetrate deeply into the world of words, colors and sounds, to master, develop and enrich oral and written communication skills. , helps to develop the ability to understand and appreciate works of art, to form a delicate aesthetic taste in them.

In addition, the integration of these subjects serves the mutual enrichment of the perception of each subject, the expansion of the students' worldview, and provides students with the opportunity to use effective technological forms and methods of teaching.

The main advantage of the integrated education program in elementary grades is that every initiative is shown by the student. That is, to choose the recommended types of activities, to arouse interest and increase the desire to learn the content of the educational material, in a word, to develop cognitive activity and form creative imagination, and to involve parents in active cooperation allows to do.

REFERENCES

1. Асмолов А.Г., Бурменская Г.В., Володарская И.А. и др. Как проектировать универсальные учебные действия в начальной школе: от действия к мысли: пособие для учителя / под ред. А.Г.Асмолова. – М.: Просвещение, 2008. – 151 с.
2. Mavlonova R., Raxmonqulova N. Boshlang'ich ta'limning integratsiyalashgan pedagogikasi. - T.: O'qituvchi, 2006.
3. Salaeva M.S. Professional darajaga erishish maqsadida pedagogning virtual mobilligini rivojlantirish / "Xorijiy tillarni o'qitishning dolzarb masalalari: muammolar va yechimlar xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy onlayn anjuman materiallari. Alisher Navoiy nomidagi Toshkent davlat o'zbek tili va adabiyoti universiteti. Elektron to'plam.. 2021-yil 5-may. - B.230-234.
4. Salaeva M.S. Psychological conditions for personal and professional development of future teachers. // Washington DC, USA International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS). ISSN: 2643-640X. With Impact Factor: 3.2. Vol.5 Issue 3, March - 2021.- P.231-233.
5. Salaeva M.S. Personal and professional self-development of a teacher to achieve a professional level. // Washington DC, USA International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN: 2643-640X. With Impact Factor: 3.2. Vol.5 Issue 3, March - 2021.- P. 234-237.
6. Salaeva M.S. Formation of teacher professionalism as an integration psychological event in the context of globalization of education // Washington DC, USA International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research Development (IJTSRD). Innovative Development of Modern Research. With Impact Factor: 6.410. E-ISSN 2456-6470. Special Issue – IDMR. April 2021.- P.114-116. <https://www.ijtsrd.com/humanities-and-the-arts/education/40073/formation-of-teacher-professionalism-as-an-integration-psychological-event-in-the-context-of-globalization-of-education/salaeva-muborak-saburovna>
7. Salaeva M.S. Formation of teacher professionalism as an integration psychological event in the context of globalization of education // Hindiston. International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development(IJTSRD) eISSN: 2456-6470 Impakt faktor: 6.005. Special Issue | Innovative Development of Modern Research, April 2021. - P.109-111. <https://www.ijtsrd.com/humanities-and-the-arts/education/40073/formation-of-teacher-professionalism-as-an-integration-psychological-event-in-the-context-of-globalization-of-education/salaeva-muborak-saburovna> <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd40073.pdf>
8. Salaeva M.S. Formation of virtual academic mobility of future teachers in the context of education information // "Образование и наука в XXI веке" международный научно-образовательный электронный журнал. ISSN: 2658-7998. Выпуск №15 (том 3) (июнь, 2021). - С.480-484.
9. Салаева М.С. Педагогнинг самарали инновацион фаолиятини таъминлашда шахсий-касбий ривожланишини психологик қўллаб-қувватлаш / Инновацион таълим: халқаро тажриба, муаммо ва ечимлар" мавзусидаги Халқаро илмий-амалий анжуман. Тошкент шаҳридаги ЁДЖУ техника университети. Электрон тўплам. 3-қисм. 2021 йил 21 апрель. - Б.405-407.
10. Салаева М.С. Инновацион таълим шароитида педагогнинг шахсий-касбий ривожланишининг психологик омиллари // "Образование и наука в XXI веке"

- международный научно-образовательный электронный журнал. ISSN: 2658-7998. Электронный журнал. Выпуск № 12 (том 3) (март, 2021). - С.567-570.
11. Салаева М.С., Джумабаева М. Таълимни модернизациялаш шароитида педагог шахсининг ижтимоийлашуви ва профессионаллашуви // UzACADEMIA Ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali ISSN (E) – 2181 - 1334 Barcha sohalar bo'yicha electron jurnal. VOL 2, ISSUE 9 (19), July 2021 Part - 1. - С.54-60. www.academscience.uz
 12. Salaeva M.S., Djumabayeva M. Formation of virtual academic mobility of future teachers in the context of education information // International Multidisciplinary Scientific Journal (IMSJ) ISSN: 2091-573X. With Impact Factor: 3.2. Volume 1. Issue 1, June 2021.- P. 36-37. Google scholarship <https://www.sciencepublish.org/>
 13. Salaeva M.S., Shoyunusova F.S. Bola shaxsini shakllantirishda ota-onalarning o'рни // Международный научно-образовательный электронный журнал «Образование и наука в xxi веке». ISSN: 2658-7998. Выпуск No 24 (том 4) (март, 2022). -С.751-754. https://www.mpcareer.ru/_files/ugd/Март%202022.%20Том%204.pdf
 14. Salaeva M.S., Shoyunusova F.S. Kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilar kognitiv mobilligini xalqaro dasturlar asosida baholanishning o'ziga xos jihatlari / “Халқ таълими тизимидаги тегишли раҳбарлик лавозимларига муносиб ходимларни жой-жойига қўйишнинг долзарб масалалари” мавзусида онлайн конференция. Авлонию номидаги педагогларни касбий ривожлантириш ва янги методикаларга ўргатиш миллий-тадқиқот институти. - Т.: 2022. –Б.64-71.
 15. Сиденко Е.А. Мастер-класс: «Инновационная деятельность учителя в условиях введения ФГОС второго поколения» // Муниципальное образование: инновации и эксперимент – 2010. – №4.
 16. Сиденко Е.А. Универсальные учебные действия: от термина к сущности// Эксперимент и инновации в школе. – 2010. – №3.
 17. Shoyunusova F.S., Salayeva M.S. (2022, November 1). Yangi O'zbekiston sharoitida yoshlar kelajagiga yuksak e'tibor // PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS, Australia, Melbourne. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7269286>
 18. Shoyunusova F.S., Salayeva M.S. (2022, October 11). Development of high-quality human capital is an important factor of society's development / Yuqori sifatli inson kapitalini rivojlantirish jamiyat taraqqiyotining muhim omili sifatida // *Innovative development in the global science*, Boston, USA. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7184486>
 19. Shoyunusova F.S., Salayeva M.S. (2022). Ta'lim jarayonida o'quvchilarni ijtimoiy faolligini rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari. ACADEMIC RESEARCH JOURNAL, 1(5), 9–14. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7227181>
 20. Shoyunusova F.S., Salayeva M.S. Yangi O'zbekiston sharoitida Uchinchi Renessansga mos barkamol avlodni shakllantirish muammolari / “XXI asr шахс тараққиёти: муаммо ва ечимлар” мавзусида 1-анъанавий талаба илмий жамияти ТИЖ илмий-амалий конференцияси, Тошкент амалий фанлар университети «Психология» кафедраси 2022 йил 20 декабрь. –Б.140-141.